

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ethe Maka**FIRST NAME:** Daniel Adrien**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2019 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
3. Some rules of Thumb for Writing Paper (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2021, 17-23)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
7. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)

JOURNEY THROUGH ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

"Seriously?!" This word was the first that came into my mind once I discovered that Academic writing (ACA-401D) is the first course I will have to go through for the Doctorate in International Public Health (DIPH). Moreover, this single word expressed both the astonishment, excitement, and eagerness that was mine to discover the course content. How pleased I was when I went through the table of contents of the coursepack and the video provided as study material for ACA-401D period one (1). Writing is not an easy task and even more international academic writing. EUCLID sets academic writing to high standards for its students. Achieving an acceptable paper conforming to international standards requires an excellent mastering of the rules for writing papers. So, let's embark on the journey through academic writing to see what it takes!

2) "CATCH THE WORM EARLY"

A familiar adage states: "it is an early bird that catches the worm." In this adage that expresses the need to start things early, I compare a good essay to the worm. Writing a good essay requires beginning early, as confirmed by the first tip for effective writing

described in chapter one of the coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 1). This is a piece of important advice because I am following my studies and working simultaneously. Hence, if I am not well organized, I risk procrastinating my assignments. How advantageous is it to start writing an essay early? Beginning to write early helps to have enough time to think about the topic, construct the initial plan, search for previous articles, organize ideas into an answer, write the essay in a structured manner, reference it, and edit it (EUCLID 2021, 1-4). What must I do at each step?

Thinking about the topic and constructing the initial plan is the starting point in paper writing. It corresponds to my "initial response to the topic or question [...] based on what [I] already know" (EUCLID 2021, 1). Researching the topic is the next step. It is impossible to produce a good paper if I do not read what others have done or said on the subject. Researching will help me obtain evidence to sustain an argument to an essay question (EUCLID 2021, 2). After getting the necessary documents, I will have to organize my ideas and decide which ones I will use for drafting. To balance my writing, I must include arguments that agree and as well as those that disagree with particular aspects of my topic (EUCLID 2021, 2). When I must have organized my ideas, I can proceed in writing the first draft.

A draft must have an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. "A draft essay will help [me] work out how [I] will answer the question and which evidence and examples [I] will use, and how [my] argument will be structured" (EUCLID 2021,3). I also appreciated the practical suggestions for writing papers given in chapter 3 of the coursepack. I felt very concerned with the idea of writing clearly. It implies avoiding long sentences and paragraphs. For sure, it is "easier said than done and hard to make operational" (EUCLID 2021, 14). But with time and practice, it is achievable.

Undoubtedly, referencing an essay, which is the next step, is equally not an easy task. However, it is essential as it avoids plagiarism. Most faculties have their referencing style, hence the need for me to be familiar with those of EUCLID (EUCLID 2021, 4). The final step in essay writing is editing. I comply that "most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing" (EUCLID 2021, 4). Reading over and over an essay helps to correct mistakes, improve on the style, rephrase sentences, add new ideas, illustrate facts, and so on. Again the key to efficient editing is to start writing early and avoid the stress of last-minute work.

3) PLAGIARISM

In the past, I happened to supervise nursing students for their dissertations. What I noticed is that most students underestimated the seriousness of citing a source without referencing it. I needed to find ways and means to help them understand how serious plagiarism is. Subsequently, I was so excited to learn more about plagiarism that I "devoured" the second chapter of the coursepack.

In this chapter, plagiarism is defined as "[using] a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2021, 5). As plagiarism

is unacceptable, wrong, unethical, and a serious academic offense, it can lead to academic penalties at EUCLID (EUCLID 2021, 5). Thus, it is essential to cite an author or a source correctly by indicating where the information came from. To achieve this, the method recommended by EUCLID is "in-text citation" (EUCLID 2021, 6). The two entities I must always cite using this method are 'quotations' and 'paraphrases.' The main difference between these two is that I quote when I use the author's exact words, and I paraphrase when I use my own words (EUCLID 2021, 6, 8). It is not advisable to use too many quotes; thus, the need to paraphrase. Not to cite when paraphrasing is also considered plagiarism. I should always keep that rule in mind as I proceed with my studies and improve my writing skills, style, and paraphrasing abilities.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter four of the coursepack on literature review began by listing eleven (11) essential reminders when writing a paper. Then the rest of the chapter goes through important rules and common mistakes or confusing words in English. I was surprised to read in this section that a sentence can begin with "and." Using this style sounded in my ears as writing in fragments. But I learned that it is possible to start a sentence with a conjunction. This style is even a "powerful rhetorical tool" as long as it is used "purposefully and appropriately," as does experienced writers (EUCLID 2021, 22).

For this chapter to be harmonious, I have identified parts of the text that had to occur in separate subheadings. On page 19, paragraphs 6 and 7 may be titled: "Should punctuations be placed inside or outside quotes?" The second and third paragraphs on page 21 can be subtitled: "When should 'a' or 'an' be used?", the fourth and fifth paragraphs: "What are the proper uses of 'good' and 'well'?". On page 22, "Which is the proper verb (singular/plural) to use when the is a fraction" should be written in subheading style.

5) STYLE GUIDE

The fifth chapter of the coursepack, though the shortest, was also one of my favorites. I always saw the Microsoft (MS) Word style tab on my computer. Still, I was never interested in going deeply into it. Neither had I any idea of what a powerful tool it can be. At my workplace, I regularly write reports—each time, I have to redo the layout, which takes a lot of time.

As I was reading the chapter, I discovered that using a style guide is very beneficial. It saves time for proofreading and style corrections and helps to have a consistent writing style even when other authors or writers contribute (EUCLID 2021, 24, 25). Today, using the EUCLID response paper template allows me to move from theory to practice. My impression: "it is easy and delightful to use a style guide!" The next step will be to create a style guide for my reports at my workplace.

6) AMERICAN ENGLISH VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Even though English is not my mother tongue, I knew some differences between American and British English. Still, I had no idea of the extent of those differences. At the end of reading this chapter, I realized that it is not easy to master all the differences between both languages. Students are free to use either American or British English at EUCLID, but they must be consistent throughout the paper. To achieve this, Professor Cleenewercke, in the video provided as study material, recommends setting the appropriate chosen type of English as proofing language in MS Word.

At some point in my reading, it was challenging for me to distinguish which type of English the examples were referring to. I noticed this issue with sub-headings like "Same Concept, Different Terms or Expressions; (or) Same Word, Differences in Style, Connotation and Frequency" on page 30, "Creativity: Spinoffs; Combos; Referencing of Current Events and Brands" on page 31, "Euphemistic References" on page 32, "Various Jargons; Changing Cultural References..." on page 33.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

Doctor Abel Scribe wrote the eighth chapter of the coursepack. In the opening words of this chapter, I discovered two new referencing styles; Chicago style and Turabian style. The Chicago style is "the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the *Chicago Manual of Style (CMS)*, 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press)", whereas the Turabian style "is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers" (EUCLID 2021, 44).

In a nutshell, the CMS covers almost all aspects of writing, either spelling, page formatting, end/footnotes, references, and so forth. It is a crucial tool to refer to as needed.

8) CONCLUSION

How pleasant it was for me to read the ACA-401D coursepack! At this point of the journey towards my DIPH, I have learned a lot about essay writing, plagiarism, style guide, and referencing styles. To attain the highest level of academic quality expected by EUCLID for its graduates, I will have to pay more attention to my grammar, style and also improve my English vocabulary. This is just the beginning, and I know that there is still a lot ahead.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.